

Isotherms Study of Equilibrium Adsorption of a Quaternary System unto Activated Carbon Derived From Oil Palm Empty Fruit Bunch

Olateju I. I.¹, Adeodu A. O.², Daniyan I. A.³

¹Department of Chemical Engineering, Afe Babalola University Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria.

^{2,3}Department of Mechanical and Mechatronics Engineering, Afe Babalola University, Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria.

*Corresponding author: Olateju I. I.

Department of Chemical Engineering,
Afe Babalola University,
Ado-Ekiti, Ekiti State, Nigeria.
E-mail: ajalaid21@yahoo.com,

Received: April 28, 2014, Accepted: May 12, 2014, Published: May 13, 2014.

ABSTRACT

Equilibrium adsorption of four water pollutants (Phenol, Butanol, Butan-2-ol and 2 Methylbutan-2-ol) using activated carbon derived from oil-palm empty fruit bunch was studied. To assess the use of activated carbon to remove the pollutants from aqueous solution, the effect of pollutants initial concentration and adsorbent dose have been evaluated. Langmuir and Freundlich isotherm model were also investigated. From the analysis of the results, it was observed that, there was progressive decrease in the concentrations of the adsorbates, thus corresponding decrease in the quantities of adsorbates per specific weights of the adsorbent. For instant, 0.1g of activated carbon adsorbed 1.08, 0.96, 1.08 and 1.0 concentrations (g/l) of phenol, butanol, butan-2-ol and 2-methylbutan-2-ol respectively. It was also observed that quantity of adsorbates per specific weight of the adsorbent is higher in butanol ($q_e = 23.95$); followed by 2-methyl butan-2-ol ($q_e = 15.10$) compared to others. This follows the same decreasing trends to butan-2-ol and phenol respectively. The regression value obtained for each of the components especially butanol which is 0.904 and 2-methylbutan-2-ol which is 0.916 shows that the Freundlich isotherm is a good fit for adsorption experimental data of butanol and 2-methylbutan-2-ol because of their regression values which is very close to 1 unlike phenol and butan-2-ol. The regression coefficient obtained for phenol is 0.904, butan-2-ol is 0.919, butanol is 0.979 and 2-methylbutan-2-ol is 0.974. This shows that Langmuir isotherm is a good fit for adsorption experimental data for phenol, butanol, butan-2-ol and 2-methylbutan-2-ol. It was concluded that activated carbon has a high adsorptive capacity to remove phenol, butanol, butan-2-ol and 2-methyl butan-2-ol from the liquid system.

Keyword: Adsorbates, Adsorption, Adsorptive capacity, Adsorption equilibrium, Isotherms

INTRODUCTION

Water pollution mostly comes from waste water which contains industrial and environmental pollutants. Petrochemical and petroleum products manufacturing cause serious problems for waste waters. They affect biodegradation, light penetration and photosynthesis [1]. Minor releases of chemical pollutants impact the aesthetics and health disorders to organisms exposed to them producing imbalances in these ecosystems [1]. Furthermore, of these chemical pollutants on passage to drinking water can cause damage to human life. For example, phenol and phenolic compounds are ubiquitous pollutants which come to the natural water resources from the effluents of a variety of chemical industries such as cool refineries, phenol manufacturing, pharmaceutical and industries of resin paint, dyeing, textile, wood, petrochemical, pulp mill, etc [2-4]. Consequently, aquatic organisms including fishes are subjected to these pollutants [5]. Phenol and its derivatives induce toxic

effect for fishes. They induce genotoxic, carcinogenic, immunotoxic, haematological and physiological effect [6-10] and have a high bioaccumulation rate along with food chain due to its lipophilicity. Thus, phenol pollution represents a threat against natural environment and also to human health [11]. Possible treatment such as steam distillation [12-13], separation by extraction [14-18], separation by adsorption [19-26], separation by membrane [27-31], destruction of phenol by wet-air oxidation [32-35], electro-chemical oxidation [36-44], biochemical abatement [45-51]. Many problems associated with the above mentioned methods have been reported in the literature such as high cost, low efficiency and generation of toxic products [52].

Adsorption technique for waste water treatment has become more popular in the recent years, owing to their efficiency. Activated carbon is mainly used to remove pollutants from

aqueous solutions, but it is very expensive. Many reviews appeared in literature about the low cost adsorbent used [53-54]. The adsorbent can be from agricultural waste (sugar cane bagasse pitch and dates stone) [55-56], industrial waste products (fly ash and red mud) [57], natural organic products (algae) [58] and natural inorganic material [59].

The purpose of this research is to determine the adsorption isotherms of the quaternary system using particular mass of adsorbent thus showing approximate adsorptive capacity. The scope of the study is limited to effect of initial concentration of the pollutants and the adsorbent dose.

In 2005 Indra Deo Mall et al [59] studied the Adsorptive removal of malachite green dye from aqueous solution by bagasse fly ash and activated carbon-kinetic study and equilibrium isotherm analyses. Batch adsorption studies were conducted to evaluate the effect of various parameters such as pH, adsorbent dose, contact time and initial MG concentration on the removal of MG. The initial pH of the dye solution strongly affected the chemistry of both the dye molecules and adsorbents in an aqueous solution. Equilibrium reached in about 4 h contact time. The adsorption followed pseudo-second-order kinetics.

In 2005 B.H. Hameed, A.T.M. and Din, A.L. Ahmad [60] studied Adsorption of methylene blue onto bamboo-based activated carbon. Kinetics and equilibrium studies Bamboo, an abundant and inexpensive natural resource in Malaysia was used to prepare activated carbon by physiochemical activation with potassium hydroxide (KOH) and carbon dioxide (CO₂) as the activating agents at 850 °C for 2 h. The adsorption equilibrium and kinetics of methylene blue dye on such carbon were then examined at 30 °C. Adsorption isotherm of the methylene blue (MB) on the activated carbon was determined and correlated with common isotherm equations. The equilibrium data for methylene blue adsorption well fitted to the Langmuir equation, with maximum monolayer adsorption capacity of 454.2 mg/g. Two simplified kinetic models including pseudo-first-order and pseudo-second-order equation were selected to follow the adsorption processes. The adsorption of methylene blue could be best described by the pseudo second-order equation. The kinetic parameters of this best-fit model were calculated and discussed.

In 2006 Ewa Lorenc-Grabowska and Grażyna Gryglewicz [61] studied Adsorption characteristics of Congo Red on coal-based mesoporous activated carbon Adsorption of Congo Red dye (CR) on bituminous coal-based mesoporous activated carbon (AC) from aqueous solutions was studied. The ACs used differed significantly in terms of total surface area, pore volume distribution and surface charge properties. The mesopore contribution to the total pore volume ranged from 52 to 83%. The adsorption tests were performed under static conditions at solution pH 7.8e8.3. The pH at the point of zero charge (pHPZC) for ACs used was over 10. It was found that the higher the fraction of mesopores with a size between 10 and 50 nm, the shorter the time to achieve the equilibrium stage for CR adsorption. The kinetics of adsorption in view of two kinetic models, i.e. the pseudo-second-order model and the intraparticle diffusion model, was discussed. The pseudo-second-order kinetic model describes the adsorption of CR on mesoporous activated carbon very well. The correlation

coefficients ranged from 0.980 to 0.991. The equilibrium adsorption data were interpreted using Langmuir and Freundlich models. The adsorption of CR was better represented by the Langmuir equation. The monolayer adsorption capacity of ACs was found to increase with increasing both the mesopore volume and the mesopore contribution to their porous texture. In 2007 R. A. Shawabkeh and E. S. M. Abu-Nameh [62] studied Absorption of Phenol and Methylene Blue by Activated Carbon from Pecan Shells. Activated carbon is produced from pecan shells by chemical activation using phosphoric acid. This activation is followed by the treatment with sodium dodecyl sulfate to prepare the surface for the adsorption of phenol and methylene blue from aqueous solution. The results showed a great ability for methylene blue removal with sorption capacity of 410 mg/g at pH 9 and solution concentration of 35 mg/l, while moderate adsorption was obtained for phenol with a capacity of 18 mg/g at pH 11 and the same solution concentration. The increase or decrease in solution pH has a favorable effect on the sorption of both adsorbates. Langmuir and Freundlich models were used to fit the experimental data.

In 2009 Tabrez A. Khan, Imran Ali, Ved Vati Singh and Sangeeta Sharma [63] studied the Utilization of Fly ash as Low-Cost Adsorbent for the Removal of Methylene Blue, Malachite Green and Rhodamine B Dyes from Textile Wastewater. Fly ash was utilized as a potential lowcost adsorbent for the removal of methylene blue, malachite green and rhodamine B from artificial textile wastewater. The adsorbent was characterized by its physico-chemical analyses, porosity, surface area, ignition loss measurements and scanning electron micrograph. Adsorption studies were carried out in a batch process with different concentrations of dyestuffs, pH, temperature and contact time. The removal of methylene blue, malachite green and rhodamine B varied from 0.228 to 0.814, 0.219 to 0.644, and 0.184 to 0.618 mgg⁻¹ respectively when the initial dye concentration was raised from 5 to 20 mgL⁻¹. The amount of dye adsorbed (mgg⁻¹) was found to increase with increase in the contact time; with 80 minutes for malachite green and rhodamine B and 100 minutes for methylene blue. The equilibrium data closely followed both Langmuir and Freundlich isotherms, but the latter isotherm fitted the data better.

Physical Adsorption (Physisorption)

The condensation of gases and vapours on solids at temperature above dew point depend upon van der Waals forces (an intermolecular attractive force). The amount of gas adsorbed relates to the ease of condensation of the gas – the higher the boiling point, the greater the amount adsorbed, although physical adsorption is usually directly proportional to the amount of solid surface available. It is not limited to a single molecular layer since a number of layers of molecules can build up on the surface. Physical adsorption is accompanied by capillary condensation with the pores which substantially increases the amount of gas that can be adsorbed. A small amount of heat is liberated (endothermic) during physical adsorption and the process is relatively rapid and readily reversible. By lowering pressure or raising temperature the adsorbed gas can be desorbed with no chemical change [65]. Physical adsorption studies are valuable in determining the

physical properties of solid catalysts (surface area and pore size distribution in porous catalysts).

Chemical Adsorption (Chemisorption)

The contaminant gas/liquid molecule forms a chemical bond with the adsorbent, and the gas is held strongly to the solid surface by valence forces [66]. Much slower than physical adsorption because of the displacement of atoms that must occur in the molecules, chemisorption also liberates greater amounts of heat (exothermic) and requires more energy in the process. Indeed, at low temperatures, chemical adsorption may occur so slowly that it is hardly measurable. Chemisorption results in the formation of a single layer of molecules on the solid surface and the process is usually irreversible because the chemical nature of the adsorbates will have been altered in the adsorption process. The amount of gas adsorbed in chemical adsorption processes depends upon pressure and temperature.

Adsorption Equilibrium

Adsorption equilibrium is defined when the number of molecules arriving on the adsorbent surface is equal to the number of molecules leaving the surface to go into the fluid phase. The adsorbed molecules exchange energy with the structural atoms of the surface and provided that the time of adsorption is long enough, the adsorbed molecules will be in a thermal equilibrium with the surface atoms. In order to leave the surface, the adsorbed molecule has to take up sufficient energy from the fluctuations of thermal energy at the surface so that the energy corresponding to the vertical component of its vibrations surpasses the holding limit [67].

Adsorption equilibrium data is typically plotted in the form of an adsorption isotherm. The shape of the curve is a significant factor in design. Favorable isotherms permit higher solid loadings at lower solution concentrations. These tend to start out steep and level out. Isotherms which start out flat are unfavourable since they only work well at high concentrations of solute.

Several fits have been proposed for isotherms. A linear isotherm seems to work for very dilute solutions but not for many others.

Adsorption Isotherms

The adsorption isotherm is the equilibrium relationship between the concentration in the fluid phase and the adsorbent particles at a given temperature [67]. Adsorption is usually described through isotherms (graphs of data), that is, the amount of adsorbate on the adsorbent as a function of its pressure (if gas) or concentration (if liquid) at constant temperature. The quantity adsorbed is nearly always normalized by the mass of the adsorbent to allow comparison of different materials.

Adsorption isotherms are extremely valuable in a preliminary evaluation of feasibility of using activated carbon for removal of a particular substance or of several substances from a waste solution. Published adsorption isotherms for toxic organic compounds are useful for comparing pure compounds. The evaluation of isotherms data is however complicated by the fact that wastes are mixtures [68].

The individual compounds in a mixture are in competition for the available surface area and the compounds with the strongest attraction will be favored at the expense of the compounds with weaker attractive forces. The amount

adsorbed is proportional to the concentration in the fluid [67]

Fig 2.1 Adsorption Isotherms

As Figure 1a and b above depict, the high level and slight slope of carbon A reveals a high capacity over the entire range of concentrations studied. Carbon B has essentially the same slope but proportionately less capacity; therefore with other considerations being equal, carbon A will be chosen for either batch or column operations.

Carbon C will have a superior capacity in batch processes up to the point where the carbon D isotherm crosses over the carbon C for counter-current column operation because of the higher capacity at the influent concentration. Column operation is generally favored by a steep isotherm slope.

Inspection of an adsorption isotherm will reveal whether or not a particular degree of removal can be achieved and will also show the approximate adsorptive capacity of the carbon. Adsorption isotherms are useful for determining the effect of pH and temperature on these systems.

Temperatures effects on adsorption are profound and measurements are usually at a constant temperature. Most steps using adsorbents have little variation in temperature.

The amount of a pure reactant (gas or liquid) adsorbed per unit mass of a given adsorbent is a function of temperature and pressure only mathematically,

$$v = f(T, P) \quad (1)$$

Where v is the volume of gas adsorbed at s.t.p per gram of adsorbent in cm^3/g

The results of adsorption experiments are most commonly presented in the following forms [69]:

Adsorption isotherms: $v = f(p)$, $T = \text{constant}$

Adsorption isobars: $v = f(T)$, $p = \text{constant}$

Adsorption isosteres: $p = f(T)$, $v = \text{constant}$

NOTE: The third result is equilibrium pressure as a function of temperature at a fixed amount of gas adsorbed. The results of adsorption experiments are most commonly presented in the form of adsorption isotherms. Isotherms are available for pure compounds, but these do not take into consideration the dynamics of adsorption when multiple compounds are present.

In a bid to explain the wide variety of experimental results, many theories and models have been proposed.

A variety of shapes of curves have been observed by the various investigations who have studied the adsorption of many different gases by many different types of adsorbents. Brunauer et al [70] suggested the classification of these results according to the five types of isotherms shown in figure 2.2. Adsorption isotherm of type I are generally attributed to un-molecular adsorption. These curves are also referred to as Langmuir

isotherm because they are described by the model proposed by Langmuir. The S-shaped or sigmoid isotherm type II is generally regarded as being descriptive of multimolecular adsorption. Brunauer [70] suggested that type III isotherm represents the formation of multimolecular layers before a unimolecular layer has been adsorbed, and that types IV and V reflect the occurrence of capillary condensation. All these curves are shown in figure 2a-e.

[2]

Figure 2a-e. Types of physical adsorption

METHODOLOGY AND MATERIAL

Adsorbent

Activated carbon, also called activated charcoal or activated coal, is a form of carbon that has been processed to make it extremely porous and thus to have a very large surface area available for adsorption or chemical reactions.

Activated carbons are highly developed internal surface area and porosity, sometimes described as solid sponges. The large surface area results in a high capacity for adsorbing chemicals from gases liquids. The most widely used commercial active carbons have a specific surface area of the order of 800-1500 m²/g, as determined typically by nitrogen gas adsorption. Difference in pore size affects the adsorption capacity for molecules of different shapes and sizes, and thus is one of the criteria by which carbons are selected for a specific application. Porosity is classified by IUPAC into three different groups of pore sizes. They are:

Micropores: width less than 2 nm

Mesopores: width between 2 and 50 nm

Macropores: width greater than 50 nm

Preparation of Activated carbon

EFB used for preparation of activated carbon in this study was obtained from a local palm oil mill. The pre-heated EFB was loaded in a stainless steel vertical tubular reactor placed in a tube furnace and the carbonization of the precursor was carried out by ramping the temperature from room temperature to 700°C with heating rate of 10°C/min. and hold 2hrs. Throughout the carbonization process, purified nitrogen was flown through at flow rate of 150cm³/min. The activated carbon was prepared using physiochemical activation method consisting of potassium hydroxide (KOH) treatment followed by carbon dioxide (CO₂) gasification by applying the optimum operating conditions obtained from earlier study [71]. The char produced from the carbonization process was mixed with potassium hydroxide pallets with impregnation ratio of 3:1. The dried mixture was then activated under the same condition as carbonization, but to a final temperature of 844°C. Once the final temperature was reached, the nitrogen gas flow was

switched to CO₂ and activation was held for 1.8hrs. The activation was then cooled to room temperature under nitrogen flow and then washed with hot deionized water and 0.1M HCL until the PH of the washing solution reached 6-7

Experimental Procedures and Set-up

The following apparatus and materials were used to carry out the experiment in the laboratory: Spectrophotometer, Electromagnetic stirrer, Weighing balance, Measuring cylinder, Volumetric flask, Conical flask, Funnel, Filter paper, Cuvette, Activated carbon, Phenol, Butanol, Butan-2-ol, 2-methylbutan-2-ol.

Experimental Procedure for Adsorption Isotherm

1. The solutions were prepared with the initial concentration of 1.08 g/l for phenol, butan-2-ol, butanol, and 2-methylbutan-2-ol.
2. A set of five glass tubes, each charged with 20ml solution of the organic components (phenol, butan-2-ol, butanol, 2-methylbutan-2-ol, was used.
3. Different amounts of activated carbon ranging between 0.1, 0.5, 0.75, 1.0, 1.5g were added to the tubes.
4. Each tube was shaken vigorously and continuously for one hour until equilibrium was achieved. The solid adsorbents were removed by filtration.
5. The samples were analyzed to determine the equilibrium concentration of each organic component in the solution with spectrophotometer of wavelength of 350 nm. The amount of adsorbates (mg/g) was calculated using the formulae reported by Vanderborgh and Griekennon [72]

$$Q = \frac{V(C_i - C_e)}{W} \dots\dots\dots 1$$

Where Q= the amount of solute adsorbed from the solution. V= volume of the adsorbates, C_i = initial concentration before adsorption, C_f = concentration after adsorption and W= the weight in gram of the adsorbent. The data was fitted into the following isotherms: Langmuir and Freundlich models. The removal efficiency (adsorptive capacity) was determined by computing the percentage sorption using the formulae in equation

$$\% \text{ sorption} = \frac{C_i - C_e}{C_i} \times 100\% \dots\dots\dots 2$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1. Concentration and Absorbance Data

Phenol Conc. (g/l)	Absorbance	Butanol		Butan-2-ol		2-Methylbutan-2-ol	
		Conc. (g/l)	Absorbance	Conc. (g/l)	Absorbance	Conc. (g/l)	Absorbance
0.407	0.091	0.405	0.111	0.403	0.097	0.402	0.098
0.646	0.101	0.648	0.115	0.645	0.112	0.644	0.116
0.856	0.120	0.810	0.128	0.807	0.117	0.805	0.119
1.080	0.126	1.080	0.133	1.080	0.124	1.080	0.131
1.291	0.138	1.296	0.136	1.291	0.137	1.290	0.140

Table 2. Quaternary Adsorption Data from an Aqueous System

Mass (g)	Phenol (g/l)	Butanol (g/l)	Butan-2-ol (g/l)	2-Methylbutan-2-ol (g/l)
0.10	1.08000	0.96026	1.08000	1.00445
0.50	1.03704	0.86093	1.02644	0.93764
0.75	1.01852	0.82781	1.00240	0.91537
1.00	1.00000	0.79470	0.97837	0.89310
1.50	0.96296	0.72848	0.93029	0.84855

Table 3. Equilibrium Adsorption Data

Phenol Ce(mg/l)	qe	Butanol Ce(mg/l)	qe	Butan-2-ol Ce(mg/l)	qe	2-methylbutan-2-ol Ce(mg/l)	qe
1080.00	-	960.26	23.948	1080.00	-	1004.45	15.110
1037.04	1.718	860.93	8.763	1026.44	2.142	937.64	5.694
1018.52	1.639	827.81	6.725	1002.40	2.069	915.37	4.390
1000.00	1.600	794.70	5.706	978.37	2.033	893.10	3.738
962.96	1.561	784.48	4.687	930.29	1.996	848.55	3.086

[3]

Table 4. Freundlich Isotherm Data

Phenol		Butanol		Butan-2-ol		2-Methylbutan-2-ol	
log Ce	log qe	log Ce	log qe	log Ce	log qe	log Ce	log qe
3.0334	-	2.9824	1.3793	3.0334	-	3.0019	1.1793
3.0158	0.2350	2.9350	0.9427	3.0113	0.3308	2.9720	0.7554
3.0080	0.2146	2.9179	0.8277	3.0010	0.3158	2.9616	0.6425
3.0000	0.2041	2.9002	0.7563	2.9905	0.3081	2.9509	0.5727
2.9836	0.1934	2.8624	0.6709	2.9686	0.3002	2.9287	0.4894

[4]

Table 5. Langmuir Isotherm Data

Phenol		Butanol		Butan-2-ol		2-Methylbutan-2-ol	
1/Ce	1/qe	1/Ce	1/qe	1/Ce	1/qe	1/Ce	1/qe
0.00093	-	0.00104	0.04176	0.00093	-	0.00010	0.06618
0.00096	0.58207	0.00116	0.11412	0.00097	0.46685	0.00107	0.17560
0.00098	0.61013	0.00121	0.14870	0.00100	0.48333	0.00109	0.22780
0.00100	0.62500	0.00126	0.17525	0.00102	0.49188	0.00112	0.26750
0.00104	0.64061	0.00137	0.21336	0.00107	0.50100	0.00119	0.32400

Figure 3a. Correlation Experimental data for Phenol using Freundlich Isotherm

Figure 3b. Correlation Experimental data for Butanol using Freundlich Isotherm

Figure 3c. Correlation Experimental data for Butan-2-ol using Freundlich Isotherm

Figure 3d. Correlation Experimental data for 2 Methyl butan-2-ol

Figure 4a. Correlation Experimental data for Phenol using Langmuir Isotherm

Figure 4b. Correlation Experimental data for Butan-2-ol using Langmuir Isotherm

Figure 4c. Correlation Experimental data for Butanol using Langmuir Isotherm

Figure 4d. Correlation Experimental data for 2 MethylButan-2-ol using Langmuir Isotherm

Figure 5a. Equilibrium isotherm for phenol

Figure 5b. Equilibrium isotherm for butanol

Figure 5c. Equilibrium isotherm for butan-2-ol

Figure 5d. Equilibrium isotherm for 2 Methyl butan-2-ol

Table 2 shows the concentrations of each adsorbate in an aqueous system for specific masses of activated carbon. Table 3 shows the adsorption equilibrium data of the quaternary system. This represents the relationship of quantities of adsorbates per specific weight of the adsorbent (q_e /mg). Different mass of activated carbon as adsorbent were used to determine the adsorptive capacity in the quaternary system.

From the tables, it was observed that, there was progressive decrease in the concentrations of the adsorbates, thus corresponding decrease in the quantities of adsorbates per specific weights of the adsorbent. For instant, 0.1g of activated carbon adsorbed 1.08, 0.96, 1.08 and 1.0 concentrations (g/l) of phenol, butanol, butan-2-ol and 2-methylbutan-2-ol respectively. When the mass of the activated carbon was changed to 0.5g, there was still a decrease in the corresponding quantities of adsorbates per specific quantity of adsorbent but not as much as the initial mass (less adsorption). The decrease in the quantities of the adsorbates follows similar trends all through, irrespective of more available adsorption sites from the increase in the specific weight of the adsorbent. Thus, activated carbon shows strong adsorptive capacity in the quaternary system. Also adsorptive capacity is more of a function of concentration for liquid system rather than adsorption sites.

The data obtained as adsorption equilibrium are transformed into graph, called adsorption isotherms. This is the amount of adsorbates on the adsorbent as a function of concentration at constant temperature. It is valuable in the evaluation of feasibility of using an adsorbent for removal of a particular substance or several substances from a solution.

Considering figure 5a-d from table 3 (adsorption equilibrium data), it is observed that quantity of adsorbates per specific weight of the adsorbent is higher in butanol ($q_e = 23.95$); followed by 2-methyl butan-2-ol ($q_e = 15.10$) compared to others. This follows the same decreasing trends to butan-2-ol and phenol respectively. Thus, the adsorptive capacity of activated carbon as an adsorbent in the quaternary system is highest for butanol, followed by 2-methyl butan-2-ol, butan-2-ol and least for phenol.

Langmuir Adsorption Isotherm

This describes quantitatively the formation of monolayer adsorbates on the outer surface of the adsorbent, and after that no further adsorption takes place. Therefore, Langmuir represents the equilibrium distribution of pollutants between the solid and liquid phases [73]. The Langmuir Isotherm is valid for monolayer adsorption onto a surface containing a finite number of identical sites. The model assumes uniform energies of adsorption and no migration of adsorbates in the plane of the surface. Based upon these assumptions, Langmuir represented the following equations:

$$\frac{q}{q_m} = \frac{Kc}{1 + Kc} \text{-----} [3]$$

$$\text{Therefore } q = \frac{q_m Kc}{1 + Kc} \text{-----} [4]$$

Taking the reciprocal and re-arranging will give the expression of a straight line:

$$\frac{1}{q} = \frac{1}{q_m K} \cdot \frac{1}{C} + \frac{1}{q_m} \text{-----} [5]$$

A plot of $1/q$ versus $1/C$ should indicate a straight line of slope $1/q_m K$ and the intercept of $1/q_m$. The essential features of the Langmuir isotherm may be expressed in terms of equilibrium parameter R_L , which is a dimensionless constant referred to as separation factor or equilibrium parameter [74]

$$R_L = \frac{1}{1 + (K_L C_0)} \text{-----} [6]$$

Where K_L = constant related to energy of adsorption (Langmuir constant), C_0 = initial concentration. R_L value indicates the adsorption nature to be either unfavourable if $R_L > 1$, linear if $R_L = 1$, favourable if $0 < R_L < 1$ and irreversible if $R_L = 0$

Freundlich Adsorption Isotherm

This is commonly used to describe the adsorption characteristics for the heterogeneous surface [75]. The results obtained in a successive series of experiments performed in statics conditions were described with basic equations of isotherms. The equation is expresses with the following general formulae:

$$q = K_f C^n \text{-----} [7]$$

Where q = weight adsorbed per unit mass of adsorbent (mg/g), C = concentration in fluid (mg/l), K_f = a constant indicative of the relative adsorptive capacity of the adsorbent and $1/n$ = indicates the intensity of the adsorption.

Taking logarithms of equation (7) and re-arranging,

$$\text{Log}q = \text{Log}K_f + \frac{1}{n} \text{Log}C \text{-----} [8]$$

The coefficient K_f and n can be estimated from the slope and by substituting the values from line fitted to a graph of $\log q$ versus $\log C$ [76]. If $1/n = 1$, then the partition between the two phases are independent of the concentration. If value of $1/n < 1$, it indicates a normal adsorption. On the other hand, $1/n$ being above one indicates co-operative adsorption [77]. The function has an asymptotic maximum as pressure increases without bound. As the temperature increases, the constant K and n change to reflect the empirical observation that the quantity adsorbed rises more slowly and higher pressures are required to saturate the surface. However, K_f and n are parameters characteristic of the sorbent-sorbate system which must be determined by data fitting. Whereas, linear regression is generally used to determine the

parameter of isotherms model [78]. Specifically, the linear least-squares method and the linearly transformed equations have been widely applied to correlate sorption data where $1/n$ is a heterogeneity parameter, the smaller $1/n$, the greater the expected heterogeneity. This expression reduces to a linear adsorption isotherm where $1/n = 1$. If n lies between 1-10, this indicates a favourable sorption process [79]

Table 4 and Figure 3a-d indicate Freundlich isotherm for phenol, butanol, butan-2-ol, and 2-methylbutan-2-ol.

The regression value obtained for each of the components especially butanol which is 0.904 and 2-methylbutan-2-ol which is 0.916 shows that the Freundlich isotherm is a good fit for adsorption experimental data of butanol and 2-methylbutan-2-ol because of their regression values which is very close to 1.

Also, considering the regression coefficient of phenol and butan-2-ol which are 0.888 and 0.887 respectively shows that Freundlich isotherm is not a good fit for adsorption experimental data for phenol and butan-2-ol compared to butanol and 2-methylbutan-2-ol.

Table 5 and Figure 4a-d indicate Langmuir linearized isotherm for phenol, butanol, butan-2-ol and 2-methylbutan-2-ol.

The regression coefficient obtained for phenol is 0.904, butan-2-ol is 0.919, butanol is 0.979 and 2-methylbutan-2-ol is 0.974. This shows that Langmuir isotherm is a good fit for adsorption experimental data for phenol, butanol, butan-2-ol and 2-methylbutan-2-ol. Their regression values which are very close to one buttress this fact.

CONCLUSIONS

- Adsorption of Butanol and 2Methylbutan-2-ol are best fit for Freundlich isotherm
- Adsorption of the quaternary system is best fit for Langmuir linearized isotherm
- Activated carbon has a very strong adsorptive capacity for the quaternary system
- The adsorptive capacity of activated carbon is higher for butanol and least for phenol in the quaternary system.

REFERENCES

1. H. A. Awala, EL Jamal M. M., (2011). Equilibrium and Kinetic study of adsorption of some dyes onto Feldspar. Journal of the University of Chemical Technology and Metallurgy, 46(1), 45-52
2. J. W. Fleeger, K.R. Carman and R.M. Nisbet, (2003). Indirect effect of contaminants in aquatic ecosystem. Science Total Environments, 3170: 207-233.
3. D. Mukherjee, S. Bhattacharya, V. Kumar., J. Moitra, (1990). Biological significance of. Phenol accumulation in different organs of a murrel, Chamna punctatus and the common carp Cyprinus carpio. Biomed. Environ. Sci., 3: 337-342.
4. D. Mukherjee, D. Guha, V. Kumar and S. Chakroborty, (1991). Impairment of steroidogenesis and reproduction in sexually mature. Cyprinus carpio by phenol and sulfide under laboratory condition. Aquatic Toxicol.,

- 21: 29-40.
5. A. M. Shalaby, M.A. Mousa and H.A. Tag Elden, (2007). Toxicological effect of butataf herbicide on some physiological aspects and the reproductive performance of Nile Tilapia *Oreochromis niloticus*, Egypt. J. Aquatic Biol. Fisheries, 11: 145-163.
 6. G. C. Jagetia. and R. Aruna, (1997). Hydroquinone increases the frequency of micronuclei in a dose dependent manner in mouse bone marrow. Toxicology, 39: 205-215.
 7. T. Tsutsui, N. Hayashi, H. Maizumi, J. Huff and J. Burret, (1997). Benzene –catechol hydroquinone and phenol induced cell transformation, gene mutation, chromosome aberration, aneuploidy, sister chromatid exchanges and unscheduled DNA synthesis in Syrian hamster embryo cell. Mutat Res., 373: 112-123.
 8. L. Taysse, D. Troutaud, N.A. Khan and P. Deschaux, (1995). Structure activity relationship of phenolic compounds (phenole, pyrocatechol and hydroquinone) on natural lymphocytotoxicity of carpt Cyprinus carpio. Toxicol., 98: 207 -214.
 9. S. K. Abo-Hegab, M. Marie and A. Kandil, (1990). Changes in plasma lipids and total protein of grass carp *Ctenopharyngodon idella* during environmental pollutant toxicity. Bullet. Zool. Soc., Egypt, 39: 211-222.
 10. H. Assem, S. Abo-Hegab and I. Belal, (1992). Comparison of haematological effect of some toxicants on *Clarias gariepinus*. J. Egyptian. Germany. Soc. Zool., 9: 33-50.
 11. T. S Hori., L.M. Avilez, K.L. Inoue and G. Moraes, (2006). Metabolic changes induced by chronic phenol exposure in matrinxa *Brycon cephalus* (teleostei chracidae) juveniles. Comparative Biochemical. Physiol., 143: 67-72.
 12. V. Janda and K. Krijt, Chromatography, 283 (1984) 309.
 13. H.G. Franck and J.W. Stadelhofer, Industrial aromatic chemistry, Springer Verlag, Berlin, 1989.
 14. D.C. Greminger, G.P. Burns, S. Lynn, D.N. Hanson and C. J. King, Ind. Eng. Chem. Process Des. 21(1982) 51.
 15. R.S. Juang, H.C. Kao and K.J. Tseng, Sep. Purif. Techhnol. 71 (2010) 285.
 16. O. Koprivnjak, V. Majetić, M.M. Staver, A. Lovrić and B. Blagović, Food Chemistry, 119 (2010) 698.
 17. F. Ferri, L. Bertin, A. Scoma, L. Marchetti and F. Fava, Chem. Eng.J.166 (2011) 994.
 18. N. Deng, M. Li, L.Zhao, C. Lu, S. L. de Rooy and I. M. Warner, J. Hazard. Mater. 192 (2011) 1350.
 19. A. Dabrowski, P. Podkoscielny, Z. Hubicki and M. Barczak, Chemosphere, 58 (2005) 1049.
 20. A. Kumar, S. Kumar, S. Kumar and D. V. Gupta, J. Hazard. Mater. 147 (2007) 155.
 21. V. Fierro, V. Torne-Fernandez, D. Montane and A. Celzard, Micropor. Mesopor. Mater. 111 (2008) 276.
 22. Q.S. Liu, T. Zheng, P. Wang, J.P. Jiang and N.Li, Chem. Eng. J. 157 (2010) 348.
 23. M. H. El-Naas, S. Al-Zuhair and M. Abu Alhaija, Chem. Eng. J. 162 (2010) 997.
 24. S. Kumar, M. Zafar, J. K. Prajapati, S. Kumar and S. Kannepalli, J. Hazard. Mater. 185 (2011) 287.
 25. R. I. Yousef, B. El-Eswed and A. H. Al-Muhtaseb, Chem. Eng. J. 171 (2011) 1143.
 26. J.C. Lazo-Cannata, A. Nieto-Márquez, A. Jacoby, A. L. Paredes-Doig, A. Romero, M. R. Sun-Kou and J. L. Valverde, Sep. Purif. Techhnol. 80 (2011) 217.
 27. M. Xiao, J. Zhou, Y. Tan, A. Zhang, Y. Xia and L. Ji, Desalination, 195 (2006) 281.
 28. M. T. A. Reis, O. M. F. De Freitas, M. R. C. Ismael and J. M. R. Carvalho, J. Membr. Sci. 305 (2007) 313.
 29. Y.S. Ng, N.S. Jayakumar and M.A. Hashim, J. Hazard. Mater. 184 (2010) 255.
 30. M. T. A. Reis, O. M.F. Freitas, S. Agarwal, L. M. Ferreira, M. R. C. Ismael, R. Machado and J. M.R. Carvalho, J. Hazard. Mater. 192 (2011) 986.
 31. C. Zidi, R. Tayeb and M. Dhahbi, J. Hazard. Mater. 194 (2011) 62.
 32. J. Levec and A. Pintar, Catal. Today, 124 (2007) 172.
 33. S. Zhao, X. Wang and M. Huo, Appl. Catal. B: Environ.97 (2010) 127.
 34. R.R.N. Marques, F. Stüber, K.M. Smith, A. Fabregat, C. Bengoa, J. Font, A. Fortuny, S. Pullket and G.D. Fowler, Appl. Catal. B: Environ. 101 (2011) 306.
 35. S. Lefèvre, O. Boutin, J-H. Ferrasse, L. Malleret, R. Faucherand and A.Viand, Chemosphere, 84 (2011) 1208.
 36. G. Chen, Sep. Purif. Techhnol. 38 (2004) 11.
 37. D. Rajkumar and K. Palanivelu, J.Hazard.Mater. B113 (2004) 123.
 38. M. Panizza and G. Cerisola, Electrochim. Acta, 51 (2005) 191.
 39. M. J. Pacheco, A. Morao, A. Lopes, L. Ciriaco and I. Goncalves, Electrochim. Acta, 53 (2007) 629.
 40. S. Song, L. Zhan, Z. He, L. Lin, J. Tu, Z. Zhang, J. Chen and L. Xu, J.Hazard.Mater.175 (2010) 614.
 41. Y. Yavuz, A. S. Kopalal and Ü. B. Ögütveren, Desalination, 258 (2010) 201.
 42. J. L. Chen, G. C. Chiou and C. C. Wu, Desalination, 264 (2010) 92.
 43. X. Zhu, J. Ni, J.Wei, X. Xing, H. Li and Y. Jiang, J. Hazard. Mater. 184 (2010) 493.
 44. P. Jiang, J. Zhou, A. Zhang and Y. Zhong, J. Environ. Sci. 22 (2010) 500.
 45. P. Saravanan, K. Pakshirajan and P. Saha, Bioresour. Technol. 99 (2008) 205.
 46. G. Bayramoğlu and M. Y. Arica, J. Hazard. Mater. 156(2008) 148.
 47. M. Shourian, K. A. Noghabi, H. S. Zahiri, T. Bagheri, G. Karballaei, M. Mollaei, I. Rad, S. Ahadi, J. Raheb and H. Abbasi, Desalination, 246 (2009) 577.
 48. X. Jia, X. Wang, J. Wen, W. Feng and Y. Jiang, Chem. Eng. J. 157 (2010) 451.
 49. C. R. Ispas, M. T. Ravalli, A. Steere and S. Andreescu, Water Res. 44 (2010) 1961.

50. H. Uçun, E. Yıldız and A. Nuhoglu, *Bioresour. Technol.* 101 (2010) 2965.
51. L. Pramparo, F. Stüber, J. Font, A. Fortuny, A. Fabregat and C. Bengoa, *J. Hazard. Mater.* 177 (2010) 990.
52. K. Nazari, N. Esmaeili, A. Mahmoudi, H. Rahimi and A.A. Moosavi-Movahedi, *Enzyme Microb. Technol.* 41(2007) 226.
53. S. J Allen, B. Kaumanous. *J. Univ. Chem. Technol. Met. (Sofia)* 43(3), (2005) , 175-192
54. M. Rafatullah, M. Sulaiman, O. Hashima, R. Ahmad. *J. Hazard Mat.*, 177, (2010), 70-80
55. N. K Amin. *Desalination.* 233 (2008), 152-161
56. Y. A Alhamed. *J. Hazard Mate.*, 170, (2009), 763-770
57. A. K Jain, V. K Gupta, A. Bhatnagar. *J. Hazard Mate.*, B101(2003), 31-42
58. D. Caparkaya, L. Cavas. *Acta Chim. Slova*, 55, (2008), 547-553
59. C. Varlikli, V. Bekiari, M. Kus, N. Boduroglu, L. Oner, P. Lianos, G. Lyberatos, S. kli. *J. Hazard Mate.*, 170 (2009), 27-34
60. Indra Deo Mall , Vimal Chandra Srivastava, NitinKumar, Indra ManiMishra. Adsorptive removal of malachite green dye from aqueous solution by bagasse fly ash and activated carbon kinetic study and equilibrium isotherm analysis. *Colloids and surfaces*, 264(2005) 17-28.
61. B.H. Hameed, A.T.M. Din, A.L. Ahmad (2006) Adsorption of methylene blue onto bamboo-based activated carbon: Kinetics and equilibrium studies.
62. Grabowska Ewa Lorenc, Gryglewicz Gra_zyna (2007) Adsorption characteristics of Congo red on coal-based mesoporous activated carbon *Dyes and Pigments* 74 (2007) 34-40.
63. R. A. Shawabkeh and E. S. M. Abu-Nameh Absorption of Phenol and Methylene Blue by Activated Carbon from Pecan Shells ISSN 1061-933X, *Colloid Journal*, 2007, Vol. 69, No. 3, pp. 355–359. © Pleiades Publishing, Ltd., 2007.
64. Khan A. Tabrez , Imran Ali, Singh Ved Vati and Sharma Sangeeta (2009) Utilization of Fly ash as Low-Cost Adsorbent for the Removal of Methylene Blue, Malachite Green and Rhodamine B Dyes from Textile Wastewater, *Journal of Environmental Protection Science* (2009), Vol. 3, pp.11 – 22.
65. L. Ferrari, Kaufmann J., Winnefeld F., Plank J. (2010). Interaction of cement Model systems with super plasticizers investigated by atomic force microscopy, zeta potential, and adsorption measurements. *J. Colloid interface Sci.* vol. 34, No.1, 15-24
66. Wikipedia, (2010). Adsorption. ([Http://en .www.wikipedia.org/wiki/Adsorption](http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Adsorption))
67. L. Wanen. McCab Julian C. Smith, and Peter Harrioh. (1993). *Unit Operations of Chemical Engineering*. Fifth edition. McGraw-Hill Chem. Eng. Series. pp 814-816.
68. R. A Dobb and J.M Cohen, (1978). Carbon adsorption isotherms for toxic organics, EPA report, MERL, Office of Research and Development, Cincinnati
69. O. A Olafadehan. (2010). Chemical reaction kinetics note. Department of chemical engineering, University of Lagos.
70. S. Brunauer, Deming L. S., Deming W. E., Teller E, (1940). Theory of Vander Waals Adsorption of Gases. *Journal American Chem. Soc.* vol., 62, 172.
71. W. Tan, Hameed B. H., Ahmed A. L., (2008). Optimization of preparation conditions for activated carbons from Coconut husk using response surface methodology. *J. Chem. Eng.*, 137: 462-470
72. M. Vanderborcht and E. Van Grieken (1977). Enrichment of trace metals in water by adsorption on activated carbon. *Anal. Chem* 49(2): 311 – 316.
73. T.H. Vermeulan, K.R. Vermeulan and L.C. Hall. *Fundamental* “ *Ind. Eng. Chem.* 5 (1966), p212–223
74. T.N Webber and R.K. Chakravarti : Pore and Solid Diffusion Models for fixed bed adsorbers. *J.Am.Inst.Chem.Eng.* 1974 20:228-238
75. N.D. Hutson and R.T. Yang .Adsorption. *J. Colloid Interf Sci.* (2000), pp 189
76. Mohan, D. and Pittman, C.U. Jr. (2006). *Journal of Hazardous materials B* vol.137, 762-811.
77. E. Voudrias, F. Fytianos and E. Bozani : Sorption Description isotherms of Dyes from aqueous solutions and Waste Waters with Different Sorbent materials, *Global Nest, The Int.J.* 2002 4(1),75-83
78. S. Mohan, and J. Karthikeyan. “Removal of lignin and tannin color from aqueous solution by adsorption on to activated carbon solution by adsorption on to activated charcoal”, *Environ. Pollut.* 97, (1997) pp.183-187
79. R. Guadalupe, H.E Reynel-Avila, A. Bonilla-Petriciolet, I. Cano-Rodríguez, C. Velasco-Santos, and A.L. Martínez-Hernández. —Recycling poultry feathers for Pb removal from wastewater: kinetic and equilibrium studies. *Proceedings of World Academy Of Science, Engineering And Technology* 2008 Volume 30

Citation: Olateju I. I., et al (2014) Isotherms Study of Equilibrium Adsorption of a Quaternary System unto Activated Carbon Derived From Oil Palm Empty Fruit Bunch. *J. of Bioprocessing and Chemical Engineering*. V113. DOI: 10.15297/JBCE.V113.02

Copyright: © 2014 Olateju I. I. This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.